

THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL SOFTWARE IN IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING PHYSICS

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Introductions. Nowadays, in our society, informatization has become the main factor of the development of the country's economy, as well as one of the causes of deep competition. In turn, informatization regulations prioritize education and emphasize the need for software.

Innovation is one of the main features of modern education. The introduction of something new (a new method, tool, technology) into learning and practice can be called an innovation in pedagogical education.

Education is one of the main links in the development of the country and its purpose is to accelerate the educational process, to direct the educational process to the individual, to classify it, to fully satisfy the needs of learners for new educational technologies. It consists of significantly improving the quality of education, education and development.

Aim. Modern information and communication technologies and software are the main source of pedagogical innovations. One of the necessary conditions for improving the content of education is to provide software in education, to create the necessary conditions for the formation and development of electronic information resources of education, and to increase the opportunities for independent learning for students.

The issue of software is basically not a new concept, but is consistent with the issue of adaptation of professors and teachers to new conditions in the process of using existing information and communication teaching tools in harmony with traditional methods.

Materials and methods. Software has a high impact on all areas of society, including education, as a result of which they have changed from a tool used to provide technical support to pedagogical technology and forms of the educational process, to education and its transformation. is becoming more and more a tool of mystery.

modern flexible education are reflected and determined by the software. For our research, these concepts are very important because modern teaching tools need to be looked at as part of a new type of learning environment and software tools need to be identified. Their development and effective use is possible only

in the conditions of a person's orientation to new educational results necessary for successful activity in an innovative society (or knowledge society).

Results and discussion. Today, the following principles of improving the teaching methodology of physics using software tools can be included:

1. The ability to use more than one way of presenting a new subject should help to represent complex electrical phenomena and processes in a way that cannot be imagined in real life.
2. Formats associated with one display element should be spatially located on one interface as much as possible. This allows the user to study the electrical phenomenon from different angles and different ways of manifestation and does not get bored.
3. Information on the subject, such as sound, graphics, text, should be used in an organized and synchronized manner. This allows not to overload a part of human perception, and also contributes to the multifaceted perception of electrical phenomena.
4. The form of the software training material should be related to the purpose of the electrodynamics curriculum and should be consistent with the educational content.
5. it is necessary to take into account the pedagogical-psychological approach to the simultaneous use of textual, visual and audio presentation forms for software educational material.
6. RTM person on behalf of ie through SHIR expression it is necessary
7. Advanced electrical concepts and electrical circuit or one _ tool through , then _ two or that one how many information present doer public information tools through present to be done need _
8. Students knowledge and cognitive features account get need _
9. Metacognitive of abilities high level with students hypertext through connections _ and each how information easily to find for amenities there is to be it is necessary

Physics is an experimental science , it is always demonstration experiment with together it is taught, but it is not a secret our republic of schools in most cases equipment deficiency there is In this mobile software of the tool main advantage is that it is how organically to the lesson adapt takes and teacher and to the student efficient help gives , again one important condition that is , the laboratory visually under conditions watching not available such physical processes or events exists , e.g artificial of the placenta land around movement . Such without demonstrations It is priceless because they are time and spatial "

squeezing " the circle and so on with together to the truth suitable coming conclusions and the results get enable gives _

software training tools are that modern computers have a large number of software with various functions that are constantly running and actively working. At the same time, there are programs that do arithmetic, make diagrams, draw, or help you stay on the line with people talking by mail. In physics, it provides a virtual display of observations such as the movement of electricity and energy consumption in energy sources. Teaching physics based on software educational tools encourages students to learn physics lessons independently. Improving efficiency in the teaching of electrodynamics is inextricably linked with the construction and study of models of electrical phenomena. Therefore, this kind of relatively new direction activity is being implemented in higher education institutions as a process of implementing physical models using virtual physical experiments.

Creation of scientifically based approaches to simplified equivalent models of physical laws is one of the urgent problems in the teaching of the Electrodynamics department in the physics curriculum of academic lyceums. Creating a new teaching method for each subject of the department is a challenge and directly leads to the reform of the teaching process.

Conclusions. One of the scientific-methodological researches aimed at the effective acquisition of knowledge by students in the teaching of electrodynamics department based on pedagogical software tools is the provision of software tools, which serve to expand the imagination of students along with the development of their thinking through computer technology models of electrical phenomena. Examples are the charged particle or Rutherford experiment models. The role of educational computer models in the form of virtual physical experiments in the teaching of electrical phenomena is at a high level.

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